

UDC: 631.1.017.3

THE ROLE OF PEASANT FARMS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE

Shuhrat Bafoyevich Adizov. Shakhzod Salimov Odiljon o'g'li,

Rajabov Azizbek G'ulom o'gli.

Bukhara institute of natural resources management

Introduction. The little family dehkan farms of household goods, personal based on the work of the family members, inheritance left to possess a plot of land given to the head of the family lifetime and will produce agricultural product of the sale.

Population in agriculture farmland in the land by themselves relevant personal free trade and cultivation of agricultural products to the needs of the family is associated with the work. State farm personal and individual plots of farmland, agriculture is not doing business does not require registration. The person operating its activities in agriculture, farmland personal self-issued as can be to handle. The owner of a plot of land allocated to him by personal farm farmland and re-grown products prepared his private property. He is married and the citizens who stand to live in rural areas for at least three years, as well as regional farmers, landowners and peasant farms and farmland of the council of Uzbekistan youth union district (city) together dehkan farms remain young citizens who have given the recommendation of the council for maintaining irrigated hectares of land to possess lands 0,35 lifetime inherited and non-irrigated (sinful Kazakhstan) up to 0.5 ha in size in the ground, the desert and the desert region, while non-irrigated pasture in size from 1 hectare is given. In rural areas of the new requirements irrigated lands on the mark for at least three years while living

quarters are not used. Thus, the size of individual peasant farms used for the maintenance of the land in housing construction previously given or to be granted land to possess inherited stay for lifetime is determined by taking[1].

Personal household economic activities can be done in the following there:

a) field plots: from the lands of the settlements accept this law until the needs of the family for the cultivation of agricultural products for purposes of free trade and the right to inheritance of land allocated on the basis of remain in their lifetime; the fund the right to remain in agricultural or forest land inherited from lifetime is designed on the basis of hectares of land allocated 0,06;

b) housing plots of individual housing construction and housing for the improvement of inherited of land allocated on the basis of the right to stay in their lifetime. Given their land to possess inherited farmland or personal stay a part of lifetime physical and legal persons without the right was saved so you can rent for temporary use. Personal stay or a portion of their land plots to possess inherited lifetime for letting me use the procedure given time shall be determined by the cabinet of ministers of the republic of Uzbekistan.

Analyzes. Peasant or farm in Kazakhstan is organized on a voluntary basis from the moment of state registration of rights to land and, in cases prescribed by the law of the republic of Kazakhstan is registered as an individual entrepreneur. The certificate of registration in the register of state entrepreneurship together based or peasant farms or to the head of the peasant farm is given. Approved by the relevant state or territorial divisions witness the revenue authorities attached a list of the members of the head of the peasant farm. [2]

Russian peasant production and other economic activities of the economy in general and together have the property (agricultural products production, processing, storage, transportation and sale) is a combination of which made relating to the property of the citizens and relatives. Personal with the participation

of their work is carried out. According to Russian law agricultural production or other economic activities which carry out a combination of citizens and property. Peasant-farmers agriculture after the state registration of his head began to work as an individual businessman[3].

Dehkan farms in Kyrgyzstan - an independent business entities who have their activity status of a legal entity or legal entities the organization of activities of the establishment basically, a family members, relatives and agricultural products, the manufacturer of agricultural land in the personal work of the other person based products or property that belongs to others and to the members of the land rent for the use of property[4].

In accordance with the law of the republic of tajikistan have reached the age of 18 shall have the right of citizens capable of dealing to the establishment of peasant farms. Peasant farm to have is determined taking the following requirements:

- legal entity without the peasant farms compared to the overall state registration of land of the land of each household member in the document of the user and reflect on joint activities of their members by a group of individuals, the rights and obligations indicated in the contract[5]. From the analysis dehkan farms in the state of which may be seen as the sole purpose, i.e., to produce specialized agricultural and food products. The main purpose of that meeting is to meet the food needs of the population and of the population is employed in the agricultural sector.

Results. The analysis shows that in the year 2023 in the republic of uzbekistan on the economic categories, the total volume of agricultural products of 88,2%i – peasant (individual plots) farms, 7,6%i – farms, 4,2%I – agricultural activities to the organization of the implementation of shows coming on. The share of agricultural products on the territory of a new analysis done on the distribution of the economic categories, the highest indicators in all regions of peasant (personal assistant) to the farm come across were observed.

2023 is the year of January-march of the months according to the results, the share of agriculture in the structure of agricultural products produced in the republic of karakalpakstan on the highest figure (12,1 %), peasant (personal assistant) in the region has the highest share of non architecture (93,5 %), the highest proportion of tashkent region the implementation of the agricultural activities of the organization (11,7 %) was recorded.

Indicators on the share of the farm in the structure of the agricultural product architecture in the region of the lowest (4.5 %), peasant (personal assistant) tashkent region the lowest share of the economy (82,6 %), the lowest share of the agricultural activities of the organization of the implementation of andijan, jizzakh region (1.6 %) was recorded[6].

Conclusion. One of the important sectors of the economy, which is in the process of increase of the population the use of agricultural land to go require a special approach. Food has been increasing from year to year because of the demand of the population. While in the same area of the land area remains unchanged. The population at them reasonable and the rational use of the land area that is available for farming if you want to own agricultural products grown up based on the culture you are going to realize that we are today. Dehkan farms were grown in their land plots to the terms of basically products out of the needs of citizens freely in the internal market is they can make a sale. This while at the same time the maintenance of citizens who live in rural areas also solved the problem of providing economic work in conjunction with no-one be our little secret.

The list of used literature

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Dehkan Farms
2. Bulletin of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020

3. Analysis of crops grown for the efficient use of land dehqan farms and homestead lands of Bukhara region. Agroprogressing Journal 2020 Special Issue. Adizov Sh. Muzafarov R.